

CooRTweet: A Generalized R Software for Coordinated Network Detection

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Abstract

This paper introduces CooRTweet, an innovative R package designed for detecting and analyzing coordinated behavior. CooRTweet's distinctiveness lies in its essential architecture, derived from a minimal definition of coordinated behavior that captures its core elements in an abstract way. This approach makes it possible for the tool to be applied to the widest range of cases, from mono-modal network analysis on a single social media platform, to multi-modal and cross-platform network analysis, and to any types of objects shared by a network, whether singular identical objects (e.g., the same tweet), similar objects (e.g., clusters of similar images), or complex objects (e.g., a combination of hashtags, images, and emojis). Additionally, it offers a comprehensive view of coordinated activities that include both explicit coordination and organic forms of content sharing. The comprehensive architecture of CooRTweet provides flexibility and a broad scope for analyzing coordinated activities across various digital landscapes. This positions it as a distinctive resource for researchers investigating coordinated communication online. More generally, CooRTweet provides a valuable example to methodologists and research tool developers of how software tools for research can be developed in a generalized and thus flexible way. This is particularly important for social media research, given how quickly new APIs are being released, modified, and even shut down. This paper aims to provide an introduction to CooRTweet and the analysis of coordinated behavior, demonstrating the software's application through a case study of cross-platform coordinated behavior during the 2021 German elections.

Keywords: coordinated behavior, social media, information campaigns, network analysis

Introduction

In recent years, a growing body of research has focused on the analysis of coordinated communication networks across social media platforms. These networks leverage the coordination of various social media accounts to influence and manipulate both user communities and the platforms themselves (Chan, 2022). This phenomenon is linked with several problematic activities, including the propagation of disinformation (Giglietto, Righetti, Rossi, & Marino, 2020) and state-backed information operations (Keller et al., 2019; Starbird et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2023).

Although empirical research into the actual impact of coordinated activities is still in its early stages (Cinelli et al., 2022; Di Marco et al., 2024), their potential consequences (Chan, 2022), coupled with the growing interest in this phenomenon for media analysis (Giglietto, Righetti, Rossi, & Marino, 2020) and its implications for the fairness of democratic processes (Righetti et al., 2022), even in authoritarian regimes (Kulichkina et al., 2024), have spurred scholars to explore various aspects of this phenomenon and develop methodologies and tools for identifying, analyzing, and informing decision-makers about these activities on social media.

This paper contributes to this area of research by introducing *CooRTweet* (Righetti & Balluff, 2023), an R package that enhances the toolkit available to researchers interested in the analysis of coordinated activities.¹ Named after Twitter, a quintessential site for coordinated message amplification through its features like hashtags and trending topics, *CooRTweet* is a versatile tool applicable to any social media platform. It can handle any type of content, including cross-platform and multi-modal networks, and enables the analysis of coordinated networks through a flexible threshold approach, allowing for the study of coordination within organic-sharing networks.

This flexibility is made possible by an architecture developed based on a minimal conceptualization of coordinated behavior, distilling definitions used in the literature down to their essentials, and thus providing an abstract definition of coordinated behavior that can apply in any empirical context. We provide this definition in the following sections, after a brief review of the literature. Next, in the usage example, we demonstrate the implementation of *CooRTweet*. We then evaluate the performance using simulated data from an original built-in function we created for generating synthetic networks, and then validate our implementation using the 86 million tweets dataset analyzed in the seminal work by Keller et al. (2019).

¹The package is available via CRAN: <https://cran.r-project.org/package=CooRTweet>.

Related Works

Coordinated Behavior

Coordination constitutes a fundamental aspect of social and communicative behavior. As Keller et al. (2019) posit, “coordinated messaging is inherent to any information campaign, which by definition consists of a group of people who want to convey specific information to an audience” (p. 259). Similarly, Giglietto, Righetti, Rossi, and Marino (2020) characterizes it as “a distinctive hallmark of user participation within online domains” (p. 872). In recent years, computational social scientists have increasingly scrutinized specific coordinated activities on social media (Mannocci et al., 2024). These activities, conducted by networks operating in a quasi-synchronous manner, are pivotal in disseminating content and narratives online. This heightened interest aligns with the broader focus on online disinformation, a prominent research theme since 2016 (Righetti, 2021). Numerous studies have documented the prevalence of coordinated social media networks disseminating contentious information across various national contexts, such as Italy (Giglietto, Righetti, Rossi, & Marino, 2020), Germany (Righetti et al., 2022), Australia (Graham et al., 2021), Nigeria (Giglietto et al., 2022), South Korea (Keller et al., 2019), Brazil and France (Gruzd et al., 2022)—as well as in transnational settings (Righetti, 2025; Righetti et al., 2025). These networks often trace back to right-wing populist movements. Additionally, research has delved into coordinated behaviors linked to the communication strategies of authoritarian regimes, exemplified by cases in Russia (Kulichkina et al., 2024). Economic motivations also emerge as significant catalysts for coordinated activities on social media (Terenzi et al., 2024).

Detecting Coordinated Behavior

With few exceptions (e.g., Chan, 2022; Rogers & Righetti, 2025; Thiele et al., 2024) the definition of coordinated behavior has predominantly been addressed at the operational level. When focusing on the detection of coordinated networks, the prevalent approach, particularly within the social and communication sciences, is to employ social network analysis to extract sub-networks of coordinated accounts from broader, non-coordinated networks. This technique relies on two key factors: the synchronicity of posts and the frequency of repetition among social media accounts. Alternative methods for detecting coordination also exist, focusing on the similarities in account features or their content-sharing behaviors (Cinelli et al., 2022;

Nizzoli et al., 2021) and the research in this area is continuously advancing (Mannocci et al., 2024). However, the synchronicity and repetition-based approach has become increasingly popular, particularly within the social and communication sciences. When combined, these two criteria create a straightforward yet effective methodological framework for identifying coordinated networks, which has proven valuable in empirical research in recent years. In developing *CooRTweet* we adhered to this established approach.

From this perspective, the detection of coordinated behavior is rooted in the notion of synchronicity. While synchronicity alone might represent random occurrences, *repeated* synchronous behavior from a stable set of accounts underpins an unusual circumstance, indicative of a centralized, indeed coordinated, operation. A key example of this approach is Giglietto, Righetti, Rossi, and Marino (2020), who conceptualize coordination as “near-simultaneous sharing” (p. 875). Similarly, other researchers, such as Gruzd et al. (2022) or Graham et al. (2020), focus on instances where accounts share identical content within a brief time frame. However, it is important to note that the duration of coordinated sharing does not necessarily need to be brief. Modifying the time parameter enables the identification of a broader spectrum of coordinated behaviors. Weber and Neumann (2021) posit that human-driven coordination activities are likely to occur within a time window of up to 24 hours, whereas quasi-synchronous coordination within exceedingly brief intervals may denote fully automated networks (botnets). Empirical research has effectively examined levels of coordination across various time frames (Kulichkina et al., 2024). Consequently, it is important to recognize that the distinction between coordinated and non-coordinated behavior is not readily definable but rather a matter of degree. While a certain degree of informal coordination is commonplace in natural conversations, both in person and online, increased levels of synchrony may indicate the presence of coordinated networks, either driven by human agency or facilitated by technology. Extremely high levels of synchronization are suggestive of botnets.

Tools for Coordinated Network Detection

CooRTweet is not the first tool for the detection of coordinated behavior. Two popular and effective tools already available to communication and social scientists interested in coordinated behavior detection on social media are *CooRnet* (Giglietto, Righetti, Rossi, et al., 2020) and the *Coordination Network Toolkit* (Graham & QUT Digital Observatory, 2020). While the

former specializes in detecting “Coordinated Link Sharing Behavior” on Facebook and Instagram, representing a seminal contribution to defining and describing this phenomenon (Giglietto, Righetti, Rossi, & Marino, 2020), the latter focuses on analyzing a broader range of coordinated activities across Twitter. Other major differences between these tools are that the former is distributed as a package for the data-science software R, while the latter is a command-line tool shipped as a Python module.²

CooRTweet extends its capabilities beyond URL networks, which was the specialty of *CooRnet*, allowing for the analysis of a diverse range of network content. In this regard, it exhibits greater parallels with the *Coordination Network Toolkit*, though it functions within an R environment. The *Coordination Network Toolkit* does indeed support different network types (Co-retweet, Co-tweet, Co-link, Co-reply, etc.). However, *CooRTweet* is not restricted to a predefined set of networks and can be applied to any type of object. The distinctiveness of *CooRTweet* from other tools, in fact, lies in its all-purpose nature, which derives from a generalized architecture and definition of coordinated behavior, which we describe in the next section.

A Generalized Framework for Coordinated Network Detection

An action a on social media can be formalized as an account u posting content p at time t , where a single account performs a series of actions A_u :

$$\begin{aligned} a &= (p, t) \\ A_u &= \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\} \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Following the standard operationalization in the literature, we define two or more accounts as coordinated when their *actions*, performed within a predefined time interval τ , repeatedly show a substantial overlap in their posted content. This overlap can be operationalized in a variety of ways: sharing the same URL, using the same hashtag, re-posting the same original post. Theoretically, sharing any kind of *uniquely identifiable content element* that can be distributed on social media. In *CooRTweet* we refer to the content elements on which we track the “actions” as *objects*, and adopt an abstract definition of “object” as “uniquely identifiable content.” Meaning that a posted content p may contain several uniquely identifiable objects o . This conceptual definition has important methodological consequences, as it imposes no limitations on the empirical definition of an object and

²With the closure of the CrowdTangle APIs on August 14, 2024, the CooRnet project has been archived. <https://github.com/fabiogiglietto/CooRnet>

the related action to be tracked, leaving this to the researcher.³ The action can be, but does not have to be, an action on the *same* empirical object. For example, it can be the sharing of the same hashtag. However, it can also be the sharing of different hashtags that are theoretically defined as part of the same category and thus operationalized as a single “uniquely identifiable content” (e.g., a combination of different hashtags all supporting a specific protest). It can include sharing the same image or images that exhibit a degree of similarity above a certain threshold. It can even involve the sharing of multiple types of objects, such as the sharing of a set of qualitatively different objects with a specific combination of images, hashtags, and mentions. Researchers are free to define the object according to their theoretical perspective and research interest. *CooRTweet* imposes no restrictions and is agnostic about the empirical nature of the object. It only requires an ID uniquely assigned to each entity defined as an object.

Each shared post (p) containing an object o ($O = \{o_1, o_2, \dots, o_n\}$) constitutes a potentially coordinated action. Formally, two accounts u_1 and u_2 fulfill the *first* criterion of coordination, when their performed actions a_{u_1} and a_{u_2} contain the same object o_i and the time interval $\Delta t = |t_1 - t_2|$ is smaller than τ : $\Delta t \leq \tau$.⁴

We group all actions (a) according to all uniquely identifiable objects (o). For every group we compute Δt for each possible account pair, yielding six values per pair combination: object o_i , both accounts u_1 and u_2 , their posts p_1 and p_2 , and their time interval $\Delta t_{1,2}$.

The second criterion of coordination is identifying users who *repeatedly* engage in actions that fall below τ as determined above. Two users may coincidentally share the same objects within the same time window, but it is unlikely that they do so repeatedly (Giglietto, Righetti, Rossi, & Marino, 2020). Such repetition is thus considered an indicator of potential coordination. With the values from the first step, we compute the edges for an undirected, weighted graph G , where the accounts are the vertices V , which are connected with the edges E by sharing the same objects. The edge weights W are the number of times two vertices shared the same objects.

³This also implies that an overlap of unique objects per single post is a possibility. For example accounts may share several different URLs in a single post.

⁴In our implementation, we also include a minimum participation parameter, which only includes users who have posted a minimum number of times. In the interest of brevity, we point interested readers to the package documentation.

$$\begin{aligned}
G &= (V, E, W) \\
V &= u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n \\
E &\subseteq \{\{u_1, u_2\} : u_1, u_2 \in V\} \\
W_{1,2} &> 0
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

We utilize percentile edge weight to represent recurrent shares by the same account pairs. By considering the edge weight distribution across the data and setting the percentile value between 0 and 1, we can identify edges that fall within the top percentile of the edge weight distribution. The package default percentile is set to 0.5 (the median), but the researchers can choose their percentile freely. Selecting a sufficiently high percentile (e.g., 0.99) allows us to pinpoint accounts who co-share an unusually high number of objects (for instance, more than 99% of user pairs in the network) in the same time window.

Additionally, we compute an “edge symmetry score” and assign it as an edge attributes, which equals 1 in cases of balanced contributions from both users and approaches 0 as the contributions become increasingly unequal. The edge symmetry score $\epsilon_{1,2}$ is determined as the proportion of the unique actions by each account to the total actions by both accounts:⁵

$$\epsilon_{1,2} = \frac{n(A_{u_1})}{n(A_{u_1}) + n(A_{u_2})} \tag{3}$$

This score, along with the value of contributions, can be utilized for further filtering or examining cases where the score is particularly low. Working with an undirected graph, indeed, it is plausible that the activity of highly active accounts disproportionately affects the weight of edges connecting them to less active accounts. This phenomenon is pointed out by Graham et al. (2024) as the time window problem, where a user caught in the net of a spammy account with high activity ends up seeing the edge weight with that account inflated due to its disproportionate activity. For instance, if account u_1 shares the same objects o_i 100 times, and account u_2 shares the same object only once, but within the same time interval τ , then the edge weight between u_1, u_2 will be 100, although this weight is almost entirely influenced by the hyperactivity of u_1 . The edge symmetry score, allows for monitoring and controlling this phenomenon.

⁵In the interest of brevity, we omit the formula for the edge symmetry score for the edge u_2 to u_1

account_id	content_id	object_id	timestamp_share
fb_12670	129235	url_23678	1629589836
fb_5966	84443	url_29871	1629589050
tw_44052	111768	url_6095	1632110137
tw_29515	39932	url_34590	1632107969
fb_20535	194917	hashtag_69114	1629583473
fb_10284	112102	hashtag_69114	1629583559
tw_50372	147781	hashtag_33126	1632108572

Table 1: An example of a dataset in the format required by *CooRTweet*. In this case, it is a multi-platform, multi-modal dataset.

Implementation in R

CooRTweet requires a dataset with four key columns: `object_id`, which represents any unique ID for content for which coordination has to be investigated (e.g., the ID of retweeted content, an ID assigned to a specific image that has been repeatedly shared, etc.); `account_id`, which refers to the unique identifier for a user account; `content_id`, which contains the unique IDs of the posts made by these user accounts; and `timestamp_share`, which provides the exact time when the content was posted by the user.

The source dataset can be single-platform (involving only one social media platform) and single-modal (containing objects of only one type, such as URLs or hashtags), or it can be multiplatform (involving more than one social media platform) and multimodal (containing more than one type of object), or it can be a combination of these elements (Table 1).

Coordination detection in *CooRTweet* is executed through two sequential steps, facilitated by the functions `detect_groups` and `generate_coordinated_network`. A snippet of code is displayed below as an example. The snippet utilizes a mono-modal and mono-platform subset of a multiplatform and multi-modal dataset of social media messages from the 2021 German election campaign (Righetti et al., 2022), which is included in the package as a non-representative sample in an anonymized format for testing purposes. Additionally, the package includes a dataset of tweets from the pro-Navalny Russian protests, utilized in Kulichkina et al. (2024). The complete script is provided in the vignette of the R package.

```

result <- detect_groups(
  fb_urls,
  min_participation = 2,
  time_window = 60)

graph <- generate_coordinated_network(
  result,
  edge_weight = 0.5,
  objects = TRUE)

```

The `detect_groups` function enables the identification of accounts that shared the same objects (denoted as `object_id`) within a predefined time interval, `time_window` (represented by τ). Additionally, the function includes a parameter, `min_participation` that ensures that only accounts with a minimum level of activity in the original dataset are included in the subsequent analysis.

The second stage of the coordination analysis is handled by the `generate_coordinated_network` function, which takes the returned `data.table` of the `detect_groups` function as input. It involves identifying accounts that performed identical actions within the same time frame, in accordance with the degree of repetition, which in social network analysis terms corresponds to the `edge_weight` (W). The `generate_coordinated_network` function returns an `igraph` object from the homonymous R library (Csardi & Nepusz, 2006), with seven edge attributes. First, the weights are stored in the `weight` attribute (W). All edges where the weight exceeds the threshold parameter `edge_weight`, are assigned a `weight_threshold` attribute of 1, and 0 otherwise. The other edge attributes are the computed `edge_symmetry_score` (ϵ), along with the number of posts published by each of the vertices in the edge (`n_content_id` and `n_content_id_y`). The attribute `avg_time_delta` represents the average time difference between the shares of objects by the vertices in the edge. The attribute `objects_id` contains the list of objects shared in a coordinated manner by the corresponding pair of vertices. An example of the function output, including attributes, is shown below.

```

IGRAPH 4790e0f UNW- 503 1645 --
+ attr: name (v/c), username_complete (v/c), username (v/c), weight (e/n),
| avg_time_delta (e/n), n_content_id (e/n), n_content_id_y (e/n),
| edge_symmetry_score (e/n), object_ids (e/c), weight_threshold (e/n)
+ edges from 4790e0f (vertex names):
 [1] fb_12670--fb_7103 fb_5761 --fb_7103 fb_12065--fb_4039 fb_11199--fb_3297
 [5] fb_11199--fb_7065 fb_11202--fb_21069 fb_11202--fb_4039 fb_18649--fb_21069
 [9] fb_18649--fb_4039 fb_11202--fb_18649 fb_2258 --fb_4039 fb_18649--fb_2258
+ ... omitted several edges

```

Figure 1: The first graph displays excluded and included vertices based on an edge weight threshold (the median), considering shares within the same time interval. Vertices are distinguished using the `subgraph = 0` option and the Boolean variable in the `weight_threshold` column. The middle graph shows how rigidly applying an edge weight threshold can result in lost information regarding the network linked to the Facebook accounts of the popular German weekly magazine FOCUS. In contrast, the third graph illustrates the same publisher's network using both wider (30 seconds) and narrower (10 seconds) time thresholds, emphasizing the importance of flexibility in considering vertices connected by varying coordination speeds, as enabled by the convenience function `flag_speed_share`.

Beyond Fixed Threshold Approaches

Extracting coordinated networks based on fixed temporal and edge weight thresholds, inevitably leads to the exclusion of accounts that do not meet these criteria. *CoorTweet* addresses this limitation by preserving data on accounts and connections that are not considered coordinated under these thresholds. This is achieved through a simple tagging method, assigning a binary indicator (0/1) to edges both above and below the thresholds.

This approach makes it feasible to examine networks of accounts that generally exceed the threshold, while also retaining those that do not. It allows researchers to explore the distribution of time intervals between shares and, potentially, to manually reevaluate the strict categorization of accounts as either coordinated or non-coordinated. It also enables researchers to consider how coordinated communication activities might co-opt genuine engagement in discussions on specific topics for manipulative purposes (Starbird et al., 2019).

The researcher has several options to investigate the networks with flexibility, enabled by the `subgraph` options in the `generate_coordinated_network` function and the `flag_speed_share` utility function. The `flag_speed_share` function accepts the output of the `detect_groups` function, where the researcher has already used a certain time threshold (τ), and allows a second, more restrictive time window to be assigned to compute

a second network. The result is a new updated output, a `data.table` that includes an additional column set to 1 when the share corresponds with the new `time_window`, and 0 otherwise. This output can be used normally in the subsequent `generate_coordinated_network` function, allowing in the latter the activation of additional ancillary options.

```
result_fast <- flag_speed_share(x = fb_urls,
                               result = result,
                               min_participation = 2,
                               time_window = 10)
```

This ancillary function enriches the result table by adding a column named `time_window_τ` where τ indicates, in seconds, the new, most restrictive time window. The `flag_speed_share` function can be executed one or more times with different time windows, creating additional columns with the respective thresholds.

The `subgraph` option in the `generate_coordinated_network` function offers several configurations. By default (0), no subgraph is created, but the generated graph includes an edge attribute `weight_threshold`, which is set to 0 for edges below the `edge_weight` threshold and 1 otherwise. Option 1 generates a weighted subgraph of edges that exceed the threshold; option 2, which requires prior execution of `flag_speed_share`, focuses on vertices showing coordinated behavior within a narrow time window; option 3, building on option 2, identifies the fastest network of coordinated vertices along with their adjacent vertices. These are just a few predefined options, and various other combinations can be achieved by utilizing the attributes and threshold markers returned with the graphs.

Multi-Modal and Multi-Platform Analysis

The main advantage of having two different functions, `detect_groups` and `generate_coordinated_network`, lies in the flexibility this approach allows, particularly in the creation and analysis of multi-modal networks. In fact, the `detect_groups` function can be repeatedly applied to different empirical objects (e.g., first to images, then to hashtags, and finally to mentions posted in content shared by the same accounts).

```
result_urls <- detect_groups(urls_data,
                             time_window = 30,
                             min_participation = 2)
```

```

result_domains <- detect_groups(domains_data,
                                time_window = 30,
                                min_participation = 2)

result_hashtags <- detect_groups(hashtag_data,
                                  time_window = 30,
                                  min_participation = 2)

result_images <- detect_groups(img_data,
                                time_window = 30,
                                min_participation = 2)

```

The resulting data tables can be concatenated, and the `generate_coordinated_network` function can then be applied to the resulting dataset. The output will be a coordinated network in which accounts are connected by edges if they have shared any considered objects (in the example, the same URLs, domains, hashtags, or images) within the predefined time window. In this case, all types of content contribute to determining the edge weight (E) between two accounts. When using a multi-platform dataset, cross-platform analysis can be conducted by marking the name of each actor with a prefix indicating the platform where they are active (Table 1). This straightforward approach helps track and differentiate between platforms, facilitating easy retrieval of information during analysis and visualization (Figure 2).

```

library(data.table)

combined_results <- rbindlist(
  list(result_urls, result_domains,
        result_hashtags, result_images),
  use.names = TRUE,
  fill = TRUE
)

g <- generate_coordinated_network(combined_results,
                                 edge_weight = 0.5,
                                 subgraph = 1,
                                 objects = TRUE)

```

This example code demonstrates another option, namely `objects = TRUE`. This option enables the researcher tracing back to the shared objects, re-identifying their type, and analyzing them more deeply. During the anal-

Figure 2: Multimodal and multiplatform coordinated networks.

ysis of multimodal data, it is also possible to examine and visualize the different types of objects separately.

The `igraph` outputs from the `generate_coordinated_network` function, run on different object types, are also compatible with specialized R packages for multiplex network analysis (Magnani et al., 2021), which offer specific sets of functions to further analyze the network.

Evaluation of Implementation

We evaluated the validity of our implementation using the dataset from Keller et al. (2019) and assessed its performance with simulated data generated by the built-in function `simulate_data`. Validating coordination detection is notoriously challenging due to the typical absence of ground truth data. However, Keller et al. (2019) examined the South Korean National Intelligence Service’s (NIS) disinformation campaign during the 2012 presidential election, where the list of participating accounts (i.e., NIS agents) was recorded and published through court proceedings. This makes it an ideal case for testing how many of the known accounts can be detected using our proposed method.

The NIS dataset was collected via the Twitter firehose API and consists of over 86 million tweets spanning from June to December 2012 and containing 1,385,730 unique accounts. Out of the 1,008 NIS accounts recorded in the

court proceedings, 801 are included in the dataset.⁶ We derive two validation tasks from the publication: total detection accuracy and suspect marking. Detection accuracy means to generate a coordination network that contains as many of the 801 NIS accounts as possible, optimized to consist of as few vertices as possible. The second validation task is to find other accounts that are suspected to be also part of the NIS campaign due to their involvement in the coordination network. Suspect accounts are identified by having some form of relationship to known the NIS account vertices in the coordination network.⁷ Given that we cannot possibly know for sure whether the marked suspects are really part of the campaign, we resort to a proxy measurement method that shows that the suspect marking is plausible. We randomly split the set of 801 known NIS accounts into a “training set” (80%) and a “test set” (20%). The purpose of the “test set” is to check whether the suspect marking method can still correctly mark withheld NIS accounts as suspects. In other words, we measure how well the method identifies NIS accounts from the “test set” that were not directly included in the “training set” but are suspected based on their network connections. Perfect performance would be 100% where the marked suspects include all of the NIS accounts from the “test set”. We repeat this process 20 times, with different random splits each time, to ensure robustness in the results.⁸

Keller et al. (2019) generated co-retweet and co-tweet networks⁹ and concluded that the optimal time interval (τ) for both networks is 60 seconds, which we also employed for our validation. For all validations, we used *CooRTweet*’s default setting for the edge weight threshold, which is the median. We generated two separate co-retweet and co-tweet networks, where *CooRTweet* could detect 731 (91%) and 139 (17%) of the NIS accounts, respectively. We also performed coordination detection with the same edge weights used by Keller et al. (2019) and still obtained comparable results. Similarly to Keller et al. (2019), we conclude that the preferred mode for this coordination campaign was by co-retweeting and co-tweeting was not widely used by many NIS agents. Additionally, we generated a combination of the two networks, which detected 737 (92%) of the NIS accounts (Table 2). In order to identify suspect accounts, we used the combined coordination

⁶For more details regarding the dataset, please refer to the original publication.

⁷The strategy for marking suspects is not fixed and there are many plausible methods possible, e.g., Keller et al. (2019) used graph components to mark suspect accounts and further explored other meta information about the suspect accounts such as account creation date.

⁸The same procedure is explained by Keller et al. (2019) in their Appendix.

⁹*Co-retweeting* refers to the coordinated retweeting of a third-party message within a short period of time. *Co-tweeting* describes coordinated behavior where multiple accounts post the same message within a short period of time.

Figure 3: Edge weight threshold variation for suspect marking on NIS dataset using a combined coordination network of co-tweets and co-retweets. A stricter threshold leads to fewer correctly marked NIS accounts and also to fewer suspects. We determine that no threshold variation is necessary and that adjacency to a NIS account is a sufficient criterion for suspect marking.

network of co-tweets and co-retweets, considering all vertices adjacent to a known NIS account in the training set. *CooRTweet* could retrieve 90.8% of the NIS accounts from the “test set”.

Turning to the performance of our proposed method, we resorted to simulated data to run benchmarks. We simulate the raw input data, as well as the ground truth data using the `simulate_data` function, according to our conceptualization as described above. At its core, the ground truth is represented by symmetric adjacency matrices for coordinated and non-coordinated accounts. The matrix values are populated by sampling Poisson distributions, which are the number of times the users have shared the same objects.

We run 1000 simulations where we systematically vary the simulation parameters,¹⁰ to generate diverse datasets.¹¹ For each simulation run, we capture the peak memory usage and elapsed time for the package’s core functions. Figure 4 shows that the `detect_groups()` function’s memory usage increases linearly with the size of dataset, but quadratically with the number of unique objects. Fewer objects, but shared by more accounts, lead to more possible combinations, and thus to an increase of memory usage and longer computations. The `generate_coordinated_network()` function requires much less memory and also scales linearly.

¹⁰See the `simulate_data` function in the package for details.

¹¹The testing system is equipped with an AMD Ryzen 7 5800X CPU and 64GB of RAM.

Network	Keller et al. (2019)		Our proposed method		
	Co-Retweet	Co-Tweet	Co-Retweet	Co-Tweet	Combined
NIS accounts in network	642	144	731 (670)	139 (146)	737 (687)
Accuracy %	80%	18%	91% (84%)	17% (18%)	92% (86%)
Minimum Edge weight	5	2	2 (5)	3 (2)	2 (5)
Vertices	3,626	2,001	22,984 (4,350)	1,579 (2,335)	24,507 (5,042)
Edges	31,755	38,035	85,557 (39,321)	36,109 (40,062)	120,958 (68,280)
Components	325	362	2,778 (372)	257 (442)	3,025 (481)
Core suspects	440	662	458 (457)	381 (678)	638 (939)
NIS accounts among suspects	85%*	-	89.9% (82.1%)	16.2% (17.9%)	90.8% (84.3%)

Table 2: Results of coordination detection on NIS dataset.

Note. The first row shows the total number of NIS accounts found in the coordination network, where the ground truth consists of 801 accounts. Keller et al. (2019)'s minimum edge weight thresholds correspond to the 97th percentile for co-retweets and the 40th percentile for co-tweets. We report results within brackets for *CoorTweet* using these thresholds, and those outside the parentheses using the default median threshold. The last row reports the testing results for suspect marking, which is the mean proportion of NIS accounts retrieved from the withheld test set (over 20 random runs).

*Results are as reported by Keller et al. (2019).

Figure 4: Benchmark Results

(a) Memory usage

(b) Computation time

Conclusion

In this paper, we introduced *CooRTweet*, a comprehensive R package designed for detecting coordinated activities on, and across, various social media platforms. This package stands out as the first R tool that is universally applicable for analyzing coordinated networks, regardless of the specific platform and content type. It is capable of identifying sharing networks involving diverse content types such as URLs, hashtags, images, texts, or any uniquely identifiable content. As a generalized coordinated detection software tool, *CooRTweet* enables the analysis of mono-platform, cross-platform, mono-modal, and multi-modal networks. Thanks to its platform independence, it can withstand changes in social media platforms' APIs without disruption, setting an example for the development of platform-independent social media analysis tools. The software's architecture has been designed to provide R users with a resource that is as comprehensive as possible, significantly expanding research possibilities, providing a streamlined solution for the efficient processing of extensive datasets.

While *CooRTweet* implements, at its core, a well-established network detection approach, it is essential to observe that there are also limitations in the method of identifying coordinated networks implemented by *CooRTweet*, as well as by other software currently available to researchers. This method distinguishes between coordinated and non-coordinated networks by applying thresholds related to sharing times and the frequency of concurrent content-sharing actions within these periods. This approach is necessarily limited to forms of coordination detectable through this methodology and does not cover all forms of coordination. For instance, recent reports have noted the presence of coordinated networks on TikTok, where accounts deliberately avoid multiple shares. They restrict themselves to sharing content only once, aiming to evade detection (Robinson et al., 2023). However, the current methodology is also limited by the rigidity inherent in a threshold-based approach. *CooRTweet* introduces more flexibility to this approach. It allows the inclusion of networks of accounts in the analysis that do not fall within the definition of coordination based on the thresholds established by the researcher but nonetheless share the same content. Manual inspection of these accounts can identify instances where they are effectively uncoordinated, serving as an organic amplification of the content in question. Another possibility is that they are, in fact, part of already identified networks, but are excluded from the analysis due to their failure to surpass established thresholds.

CooRTweet has been rigorously validated, confirming the reliability and

credibility of its outputs. Using the Keller et al. (2019) dataset, we overcame the typical lack of ground truth that makes it unlikely to validate coordinated network detection. Our results from *CooRTweet* analysis show high correspondence with the ground truth data, with about 85% to over 92% accuracy, depending on the adopted edge weight threshold. This provides a valuable resource for researchers seeking an established methodology on which to base their research efforts. However, it's important to remember that *CooRTweet* targets a specific type of coordinated activity based on synchronized co-sharing, while other forms of coordination may fall outside its scope. Future releases could expand detection to cover additional coordination patterns. Even the NIS network in Keller et al. (2019) represents just one among many types of coordinated networks, and the constant evolution of content dissemination strategies underscores the need for ongoing development of detection methods.

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